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Research Article

A NEW ANALYTICAL RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATION OF CILNIDIPINE IN BULK AND MARKETED PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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Abstract:

A novel, simple, accurate, precise, sensitive and specific analytical RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the quantitative estimation of Cilnidipine in bulk drugs and pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6×250mm, 5µm) analytical column using mobile phase composition of methanol and Phosphate Buffer in ratio of (35: 65 v/v) that was set at a flow rate of 1.0µl/min with detection of 235 nm. The retention time of Cilnidipine was found to be 3.006min. The drug was analyzed by following the guidelines of International conference on Harmonization (ICH). This drug showing linearity in the concentration range of 6-14µg/ml and the correlation coefficient showing R² = 0.9996. The % Recoveries showing within the limits. The presentation of the method was validated according to the present ICH guidelines for accuracy, precision and robustness, Linearity, limit of quantification, limit of detection linearity.

Key Words: Cilnidipine, RP-HPLC, Method Development, Accuracy, Precision.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cilnidipine is a dihydropyridine calcium antagonist. It was jointly developed by Fuji Viscera Pharmaceutical Company, Japan and Ajinomoto, Japan and approved in 1995. Compared with other calcium antagonists, Cilnidipine can act on the N-type calcium channel that existing sympathetic nerve end besides acting on L-type calcium channel that similar to most of the calcium antagonists¹. This drug is approved in China, Japan, Korea, India, and several countries in the European Union. Cilnidipine is a diesterified 1, 4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid. A calcium channel blocker, it is used as an antihypertensive². It has a role as a calcium channel blocker, an antihypertensive agent and a cardiovascular drug. It is a dihydropyridine, a 2-methoxyethyl ester and a C-nitro compound. CILNIDIPINE is a small molecule drug with a maximum clinical trial phase of III (across all indications) and has 3 investigational indications³. The IUPAC Name of Cilnidipine is (3R)-3-cyclopentyl-3-[4-(7H-pyrrolo [2, 3-d] pyrimidin-4-yl) pyrazol-1-yl] propanenitrile. The Chemical Structure of Cilnidipine is shown in fig-1.

Fig-1: Chemical Structure of Cilnidipine

EXPERIMENTAL**Materials**

Cilnidipine API and Marketed Formulation were provided by Synpharma Research Lab, Dilsuknagar, Hyderabad. HPLC grade acetonitrile and phosphoric acid, Dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate, Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate, Sodium hydroxide, Hydrochloric acid, 3% Hydrogen Peroxide were purchased from SD fine-Chem Ltd; Mumbai. HPLC grade water was obtained from SD fine-Chem Ltd; Mumbai.

Apparatus and Chromatographic Conditions

Analysis was performed using a Waters HPLC with Empower2 Software with Isocratic with UV-Visible Detector was provided from Synpharma Research Lab, Dilsuknagar, Hyderabad. This Instrument is connected to a Symmetry ODS C₁₈ (4.6×250mm, 5µm) supplied with an isocratic pump and an auto-sampling device. The experiments were operated at ambient temperature. The mobile phase⁴ was composed of a mixture of Methanol and Phosphate Buffer (35:65%) v/v. The mobile phase flow-rate was 1.0 mL/min. The detection was performed using a UV detector at wavelength 235 nm.

HPLC Method Development:**Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines³⁰.

Mobile Phase Optimization:

Initially the mobile phase tried was Methanol and Methanol: Water with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to Methanol: Phosphate Buffer in proportion 35:65% v/v.

Optimization of Column:

The method was performed with various C₁₈ columns like, X- bridge column, Xterra, and C₁₈ column. Symmetry ODS C₁₈ (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution⁵ at 1ml/min flow.

Preparation of Buffer and Mobile Phase:**Preparation of Potassium dihydrogen Phosphate (KH₂PO₄) buffer (pH-3.6):**

Dissolve 6.8043 of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000 ml HPLC water and adjust the pH 3.6 with diluted orthophosphoric acid. Filter and sonicate⁶ the solution by vacuum filtration and ultra-sonication.

Preparation of Mobile Phase:

Accurately measured 350 ml (35%) of Methanol, 650 ml of Phosphate buffer (65%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultra sonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration⁷.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Method Validation Parameters**System Suitability**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC⁸. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Specificity:**Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Weight 10 mg equivalent weight of Cilnidipine sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and add about 7mL of Diluent⁹ and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Further pipette 0.1ml of Cilnidipine above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

Inject the three replicate injections of standard and sample solutions and calculate the assay¹⁰⁻¹¹ by using formula:

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{(A_{\text{sample}} - A_{\text{blank}}) \times V_{\text{Sfactor}} \times \text{Eq. wt} \times LC}{W_{\text{sample}}}$$

Linearity:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of Level – I (6ppm of Cilnidipine):

Take 0.6ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate¹² the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – II (8ppm of Cilnidipine):

Take 0.8ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – III (10ppm of Cilnidipine):

Take 0.1ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – IV (12ppm of Cilnidipine):

Take 0.12ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – V (14ppm of Cilnidipine):

Take 0.14ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Procedure:

Inject each level into the chromatographic system¹³ and measure the peak area.

Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient¹⁴.

Precision**Repeatability****Preparation of Cilnidipine Product Solution for Precision:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD¹⁵ for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Intermediate Precision:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness¹⁶) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure:**Analyst 1:**

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Analyst 2:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits¹⁷.

Accuracy:**For Preparation of 50% Standard Stock Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.05ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For Preparation of 100% Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and

sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For Preparation of 150% Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.15ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

Inject the Three replicate injections of individual concentrations (50%, 100%, 150%) were made under the optimized conditions. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Cilnidipine and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values¹⁸.

Robustness:

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results. The following conditions are checked for variation of results. .

For preparation of Standard Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Cilnidipine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Cilnidipine stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Effect of Variation of Flow Conditions:

The sample was analyzed at 0.9 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min instead of 1ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms¹⁹ were recorded.

Effect of Variation of Mobile Phase Organic Composition:

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. Methanol: Phosphate Buffer was taken in the ratio and 40:60, 30:70 instead (35:65), remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Method Development

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:

Mobile phase ratio	: Methanol: Phosphate Buffer (35:65) V/V
Column	: Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6 \times 250mm, 5 μ m)
Column temperature	: Ambient
Wavelength	: 235nm
Flow rate	: 1ml/min
Injection volume	: 10 μ l
Run time	: 8min

Fig-2: Chromatogram of Optimized Chromatographic Condition

Method Validation

Method validation²⁰⁻²² is the process used to confirm that the analytical procedure employed for a specific test is suitable for its intended use. Results from method validation can be used to judge the quality, reliability and consistency of analytical results; it is an integral part of any good analytical practice.

System Suitability:**Table-1: Results of System Suitability for Cilnidipine**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area (μV*sec)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Cilnidipine	3.008	1652847	185647	6589	1.24
2	Cilnidipine	3.005	1653658	186254	6587	1.26
3	Cilnidipine	3.001	1654521	185475	6584	1.28
4	Cilnidipine	3.000	1653564	186594	6582	1.29
5	Cilnidipine	3.001	1658745	185684	6895	1.24
Mean			1654667			
Std. Dev.			2355.764			
% RSD			0.142371			

Specificity

The ICH documents define specificity as the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components.

Analytical method was tested for specificity²³ to measure accurately quantities of Cilnidipine in drug product.

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of Cilnidipine in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99.86%.

Linearity**Chromatographic Data for Linearity Study:****Table-2: Data for Linearity of Cilnidipine**

Concentration μg/ml	Average Peak Area
6	1078475
8	1461129
10	1808358
12	2211573
14	2593778

Fig-3: Linearity Curve of Cilnidipine

Linearity Plot:

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Cilnidipine is a straight line.

$$Y = mx + c$$

$$\text{Slope (m)} = 185008$$

$$\text{Intercept (c)} = 16179$$

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient (r)} = 0.999$$

Validation Criteria: The response linearity²⁴ is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 0.16179. These values meet the validation criteria.

Precision:

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions.

Repeatability: Obtained Five (5) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD²⁵.

Table-3: Results of Repeatability for Cilnidipine:

S. No.	Peak Name	Retention time	Area ($\mu\text{V} \cdot \text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Cilnidipine	3.008	1658954	186958	1.26	6785
2	Cilnidipine	3.000	1658745	187548	1.27	6854
3	Cilnidipine	3.013	1659865	189854	1.26	6852
4	Cilnidipine	3.006	1653254	186985	1.25	6784
5	Cilnidipine	3.001	1654781	189542	1.24	6895
Mean			1657120			
Std. Dev			2913.592			
%RSD			0.175823			

Intermediate Precision:

The Intermediate Precision²⁶ consists of two methods:-

Intra Day: In Intra Day process, the 50%, 100% and 150% concentration are injected at different intervals of time in same day.

Inter Day: In Inter Day process, the 50%, 100% and 150% concentration are injected at same intervals of time in different days.

Table-4: Results of Intra-Assay & Inter-Assay

Conc. of Cilnidipine (API) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Observed Conc. of Cilnidipine ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) by the Proposed Method			
	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Mean (n=6)	% RSD	Mean (n=6)	% RSD
50	49.38	0.56	49.45	0.56
100	100.17	0.71	99.70	0.77
150	150.89	0.89	149.91	0.85

Observations: The intra & inter day variation of the method was carried out for standard deviation & % RSD (% RSD < 2%) within a day & day to day variations for Cilnidipine revealed that the proposed method is precise.

Accuracy:

Accuracy²⁷ at different concentrations (50%, 100%, and 150%) was prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Table-5: The Accuracy Results for Cilnidipine

% Concentration (at Specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	109068.3	5	5.021	100.420%	100.72%
100%	202187	10	10.054	100.540%	
150%	297032.3	15	15.181	101.206%	

Limit of Detection for Cilnidipine

The detection limit²⁸ of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Result:

= 1.2 μ g/ml

Quantitation Limit

The quantitation limit²⁹ of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined.

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Result:

= 3.6 μ g/ml

Robustness

The robustness was performed for the flow rate variations from 0.9 ml/min to 1.1ml/min and mobile phase ratio variation from more organic phase to less organic phase ratio for Cilnidipine. The method is robust only in less flow condition. The standard of Cilnidipine was injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor, asymmetric factor, and plate count.

Table-6: Result of Method Robustness Test

Change in Parameter	% RSD
Flow (1.1 ml/min)	0.68
Flow (0.9 ml/min)	0.39
Temperature (27°C)	0.54
Temperature (23°C)	0.63
Wavelength of Detection (280 nm)	0.91
Wavelength of detection (270 nm)	0.93

Table-7: Assay of Cilnidipine Tablets

Brand Name of Capsules	Labelled amount of Drug (mg)	Mean (\pm SD) amount (mg) found by the proposed method (n=5)	Assay + % RSD
Cilaheart-10 Tablet (Mankind)	10mg	9.853 (\pm 0.765)	99.476 % (\pm 0.347)

Result & Discussion: The %Purity of Cilaheart-10 Tablet containing Cilnidipine was found to be 99.476 % (\pm 0.347).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

To develop a precise, linear, specific & suitable stability indicating RP-HPLC method for analysis of Cilnidipine, different chromatographic conditions were applied & the results observed are

Acceptance Criteria: The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Estimation of Cilnidipine in TABLET Dosage Form

Twenty tablets were taken and the I.P. method was followed to determine the average weight. Above weighed tablets were finally powdered and triturated well. A quantity of powder equivalent to 10 mg of drug were transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask, and 8 ml of mobile phase was added and solution was sonicated for 15 minutes, there after volume was made up to 10 ml with same solvent. Then 1ml of the above solution was diluted to 10 ml with HPLC grade methanol. The solution was filtered through a membrane filter (0.45 μ m) and sonicated to degas. From this stock solution (1.0 ml) was transferred to five different 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume was made up to 10 ml with same solvent system.

The solution prepared was injected in five replicates into the HPLC system and the observations were recorded.

A duplicate injection of the standard solution was also injected into the HPLC system and the peak areas were recorded. The data are shown in Table-7.

ASSAY

%

$$\text{Assay} = \frac{\text{AT} \times \text{AS} \times \text{WS} \times \text{DS} \times \text{DT} \times \text{P}}{\text{WT} \times 100 \times \text{AW} \times \text{LC}} \times 100$$

Where:

AT = Peak Area of Cilnidipine obtained with test preparation

AS = Peak Area of Cilnidipine obtained with standard preparation

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg

WT = Weight of sample taken in mg

DS = Dilution of Standard solution

DT = Dilution of sample solution

P = Percentage purity of working standard

Results obtained are tabulated below:

presented in previous chapters. Isocratic elution is simple, requires only one pump & flat baseline separation for easy and reproducible results. So, it was preferred for the current study over gradient elution. In case of RP-HPLC various columns are

available, but here Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6×250mm, 5µm) column was preferred because using this column peak shape, resolution and absorbance were good. Mobile phase & diluent for preparation of various samples were finalized after studying the solubility of API in different solvents of our disposal (methanol, acetonitrile, water, 0.1N NaOH, 0.1NHCl). Cilnidipine was found to be Very slightly soluble in water, sparingly soluble in methanol, slightly soluble in methylene chloride, very slightly soluble in acetonitrile, freely soluble in acetone, in anhydrous ethanol. Using these solvents with appropriate composition newer methods can be developed and validated. Detection wavelength was selected after scanning the standard solution of drug over 200 to 400nm. From the U.V spectrum of Cilnidipine it is evident that most of the HPLC work can be accomplished in the wavelength range of 235 nm conveniently. Further, a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min & an injection volume of 10µl were found to be the best analysis. The result shows the developed method is yet another suitable method for assay which can help in the analysis of Cilnidipine in different formulations.

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